

BETTER TOGETHER: THE ROLE OF DIASPORA CHRISTIANS IN BRINGING
HARMONIOUS DIVERSITY TO THE AMERICAN CHURCH

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1. Introduction

Segregation and Secularization

“The church is still the most segregated major institution in America.” Martin Luther King Jr. made this claim nearly sixty years ago in response to a question from Western Michigan University president James Miller during a symposium on “The Conscience of America.” The question posed to King was, “Don't you feel that integration can only be started and realized in the Christian church, not in schools or by other means? This would be a means of seeing just who are true Christians.” King replied, “As a preacher, I would certainly have to agree with this.” But then King went on to say that the church had missed the opportunity and would “stand under the judgment of God.” He then repeated his famous line, “At eleven o'clock on Sunday morning when we stand and sing and Christ has no east or west, we stand at the most segregated hour in this nation.” King believed the solution to divisions in society should've started in the church, but he felt that society must not “wait on a spiritual and moribund church” to act.¹

Sixty years later America is more diverse, but the church is more segregated than ever. In King's day, “white persons constituted 88.6 percent of the total population.”² Today, with the rise of globalization and migration, the percent who identify as “White alone, not Hispanic or Latino” is 58.4%.³ But even as the country has grown more diverse, multiracial churches have only

¹ “Dr. Martin Luther King Jr.'s visit to WMU,” interview by James Miller, December 18, 1963, <https://libguides.wmich.edu/mlkatwmu/speech>.

² “1960 Census of Population,” U.S. Census Bureau, <https://www.census.gov/library/publications/1961/dec/pc-s1-10.html>.

³ “Population Estimates: July 1, 2024,” U.S. Census Bureau, <https://www.census.gov/quickfacts/fact/table/US/PST045224>. The US Census Bureau did not begin to measure “Hispanic or Latino” until the 1970 census. The Hispanic population in the U.S. grew from 9.6 million in 1970 to 62.1 million in 2020. See Cary Funk and Mark Hugo Lopez, *A Brief Statistical Portrait of U.S. Hispanics*, Pew Research Center, June 14, 2022, <https://www.pewresearch.org/science/2022/06/14/a-brief-statistical-portrait-of-u-s-hispanics/>.

grown from 6% to 16% in the past 25 years.⁴ Much progress has been made to integrate marginalized populations into every sector of American society, but the American church has remained largely segregated.⁵ David Stevens estimates that, “Churches are ten times more segregated than the neighborhoods in which they are located and twenty times more segregated than nearby public schools.”⁶ He concludes, “The perennial question must be asked – If the kingdom of heaven is not segregated, why on earth is the church?”⁷

While racial segregation poses an internal threat to the witness of the American church, secularization poses an external threat. Lesslie Newbiggin came to the realization that churches in the West had become ineffective at reaching a secularizing society. Newbiggin wrote, “I have come more and more to feel that England is a foreign mission field as much as India was for me in 1936.”⁸ Newbiggin believed secularization resulted from an increasing dichotomy between “the public world of facts and the private world of values.” Western society was no longer asking questions about purpose but instead “What purpose does this serve?” Christianity, in Newbiggin’s estimation, no longer provided compelling answers to society’s questions.

⁴ Kevin D Dougherty, Mark Chaves, and Michael O. Emerson, “Racial Diversity in U.S. Congregations, 1998–2019,” *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion* 59, no. 4 (December 2020): 651–62. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jssr.12681>. Another study of 15,000 US congregations found that close to 25% are “multiracial.” See Scott Thumma, “Twenty Years of Congregational Change: The 2020 Faith Communities Today Overview,” Hartford Institute for Religion Research, accessed May 1, 2025, <https://faithcommunitiestoday.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Faith-Communities-Today-2020-Summary-Report.pdf>.

⁵ The term “American church” is used throughout this paper rather than the more political or geographical term “US church.” The writer recognizes that all countries in the Western hemisphere could accurately be designated “American.” The choice to use the term here to describe the estimated 350,000 churches located in the United States of America was based on the common usage of the term in academic and historical sources.

⁶ David Stevens, “God’s New Humanity in Diaspora: A Church *of* the Nations and *for* the Nations,” in *Diaspora Missions: Reflections on Reaching the Scattered Peoples of the World*, Evangelical Missiological Society Series 23, eds. Michael Pocock and Enoch Wan, (Pasadena: William Carey Library Publishers, 2015), 109.

⁷ Stevens, 122.

⁸ Newbiggin, Lesslie, “Our Missionary Responsibility in the Crisis of Western Culture” <https://newbigginresources.org/1989-our-missionary-responsibility-in-the-crisis-of-western-culture/>, 2-3.

Confronted by an increasingly secular society, the American church began to lose ground. According to Gallup, “only three in ten U.S. adults attend religious services regularly,” down from 42% only two decades ago (only 22% of young adults attend).⁹ Ryan Burge, a pastor and political science professor, “believes about a third of the country's 350,000 Christian congregations are ‘on the brink of extinction.’”¹⁰ As long as divisions remain, the American church will be powerless to reach secular society. Ironically, if not for recent trends in migration, the decline of the American church would be even more precipitous. Timothy Tennent has said, “The immigrant population actually presents the greatest hope for Christian renewal in North America... This group of people we want to keep out is the group that we most need for spiritual transformation.”¹¹ The American church needs divine help to heal the open wounds of segregation and to confront the challenge of secularization. In part, that divine help may already be migrating across the Southern border.

Thesis

Jesus prayed for his disciples to be unified and for the world to believe through their witness. For Francis Schaeffer, the loving unity displayed by Jesus’s disciples was “the final apologetic.” Reflecting on Jesus’s prayer for his disciples in John 17, Schaeffer wrote,

What is the final apologetic? ‘That they all may be one: as thou, Father, art in me, and I in thee, that they also may be one in us: that the world may believe that thou hast sent me.’ This is the final apologetic... We cannot expect the world to believe that the Father

⁹ Jeffrey M. Jones, “Church Attendance Has Declined in Most U.S. Religious Groups,” *Gallup*, March 25, 2024, <https://news.gallup.com/poll/642548/church-attendance-declined-religious-groups.aspx>.

¹⁰ Scott Neuman, “The faithful see both crisis and opportunity as churches close across the country” *National Public Radio*, May 17, 2023, <https://www.npr.org/2023/05/17/1175452002/church-closings-religious-affiliation>.

¹¹ Timothy Tennent, “Christian Perspective on Immigration,” *Seedbed*, June 22, 2011, video, <https://youtu.be/WHx95cuXpUE?si=xPxtw9TZ1eWDoNvc>.

sent the Son, that Jesus' claims are true, and that Christianity is true, unless the world sees some reality of the oneness of true Christians.¹²

Schaeffer, like Newbiggin, realized that truth alone will not grab the attention of a secular society that has abandoned absolute truth.¹³ The world needs to see truth embodied in a loving community of Christ's disciples. Sadly, the American church has become a dismembered, segregated body with declining influence in modern society. Monocultural churches located in multicultural neighborhoods will increasingly struggle to provide a true representation of the body of Christ. Transformation is not likely to come from a declining church plagued by division. Rather than dividing into racially segregated churches, this paper will demonstrate that diaspora Christians, when welcomed into and recognized as honored members within multicultural churches, offer the greatest help for revitalizing the American church and renewing a compelling witness in the world. The following questions will guide the research: First, does the Bible encourage Christians from diverse cultural backgrounds to worship together in one church? If so, what contemporary approaches to church life come the closest to the biblical approach and, therefore, are more likely to be a compelling witness to the world? Finally, how can diaspora Christians help revitalize the American church toward greater biblical faithfulness and evangelistic effectiveness?

¹² Francis A. Schaeffer, *The Mark of the Christian* (Westmont: InterVarsity Press, 2013), 26-27.

¹³ Schaeffer is not rejecting the importance of biblical truth. He continues, "The church is to judge whether a man is a Christian on the basis of his doctrine, the propositional content of his faith, and then his credible profession of faith...The church has a right to judge, in fact it is commanded to judge, a man on the content of what he believes and teaches. But we cannot expect the world to judge that way because the world cares nothing about doctrine. And that is especially true in the second half of the twentieth century when, on the basis of their epistemology, men no longer believe even in the possibility of absolute truth...But Jesus did give the mark that will arrest the attention of the world, even the attention of the modern man who says he is just a machine...What is it? The love that true Christians show for each other and not just for their own party." Schaeffer, 27-28.

2. Biblical Support

Divisions based on ethnicity, language, gender, or social status are not found in the New Testament. Where such divisions occur, the apostles wrote letters to promote reconciliation. Geography seems to be the only acceptable division separating God's people in the New Testament. The church in Antioch, after all, is not the church in Jerusalem. There are acceptable reasons to separate from individuals who themselves are divisive or unrepentant (see 1 Cor 5:5; Gal 1:9; Ti 3:10; 1 Jn 2:19). But all true believers in a city or geographical region were to be members of one body. Vignettes from the churches in Jerusalem, Antioch, Corinth, and Ephesus are given below as biblical evidence of churches positively influencing society around them through a display of unity and harmonious diversity.

The Church in Jerusalem – the number of disciples increased greatly.

The explosive growth of the church in Jerusalem eventually strained the relationship between culturally Hellenistic and culturally Hebraic Jews. Rather than responding with segregation, the apostles wisely pursued harmonization between both groups. This unifying action led to even greater effect in Jewish society. Though staggering, the early numerical growth of the church was at least measurable:

- “Three thousand people were added (προσετέθησαν) to them” (Acts 2:41).
- “But many of those who heard the message believed, and the number (ἀριθμὸς) of the men came to about five thousand” (Acts 4:4).
- “Believers were added (προσετίθεντο) to the Lord in increasing numbers (μᾶλλον) — multitudes of both men and women” (Acts 5:14).

The use of *prostithēmi* in Acts 2:41 and 5:14 indicates addition or repetition. But in chapter six the author shifts from addition to multiplication with the use of *plēthunō* (“to multiply”) and no longer gives a numerical estimate: “In those days, as the disciples were increasing in number (πληθύνοντων)...” (Acts 6:1a). Then, there is an even more dramatic shift from verse one to

verse seven: “So the word of God spread, the disciples in Jerusalem increased (ἐπληθύνετο) greatly (σφόδρα) in number (ἀριθμὸς), and a large group of priests became obedient to the faith” (Acts 6:7).

The fact that “the word of God spread” (Acts 6:7a) indicates that the apostles were faithful in their decisions and were now able to focus on further evangelistic preaching. The next result, “the disciples in Jerusalem increased greatly in number,” indicates the fruitfulness of their actions.¹⁴ The final result is the most illuminating: “and a large group of priests became obedient to the faith” (Acts 6:7c). The note on such a large group of priests is taken by F. F. Bruce to mean “that the ties which attached many of the believers to the temple order would be strengthened.”¹⁵ Bruce supposes that the inclusion of the priests may have made things more difficult for Stephen who would later argue “that the temple order was now superseded.”¹⁶ Whatever negative consequences would later result from the inclusion of the priests should not distract from the positive effects that brought them into the church in the first place. Could it be that the large group of priests were frustrated with how the temple order had failed to care for widows (see Mk 12:38-40; Jas 1:27) and were now open to the gospel message due to the harmonious witness of the church? Luke’s note on the inclusion of the priests powerfully demonstrates how the gospel was penetrating to the deepest levels of Jewish society.

¹⁴ David Peterson agrees, “Satisfactory resolution of the conflict in the Jerusalem church made it possible for this ministry of the gospel to flourish and for church growth to take place even more rapidly (*sphodra*). Church growth continued because the word of God had free course amongst the believers, and outsiders were able to witness its practical effect in a loving, united community, as well as hear its challenge from the lips of the apostles.” David Peterson, *The Acts of the Apostles*, Pillar New Testament Commentary, Accordance electronic edition, version 1.0 (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2009), 235.

¹⁵ F. F. Bruce, *The Book of the Acts*. Rev. ed., The New International Commentary on the New Testament (Grand Rapids, Mich: Eerdmans, 2009), 123.

¹⁶ Bruce.

The Church in Antioch – the disciples were first called Christians.

Soon, persecution forcibly displaced many Jewish-background Christians who had become Christians in Jerusalem. Some of these Jewish refugees would successfully establish a vibrant multicultural church in Antioch, the third largest city in the Roman Empire (Acts 11:19-20). Miriam Adeney writes, “Due to the persecution of Christians (both Jewish and Greek) in Jerusalem, many of the followers of Jesus, as followers of ‘The Way’, ended up in multicultural Antioch.”¹⁷ Jehu Anciles describes the resulting church as, “a multiethnic congregation with leaders from diverse cultural backgrounds (Acts 13:1).”¹⁸ The faithfulness and fruitfulness of this multicultural church was noticed by the larger pagan society. According to Simon J. Kistemaker, followers of Jesus referred to themselves as “brothers, disciples, believers, or saints.”¹⁹ But soon, a new term was used to describe the phenomenon of Jews and Gentiles worshiping together: “The disciples were first called Christians at Antioch” (Acts 11:26c). Though the term Christian may have been used pejoratively by some (1 Pt 4:16), it is more likely that it was first given by the pagan citizens of Antioch to describe the unique association of Jews and Gentiles together in one social group. Howard Marshall comments, “The verb ‘were called’ implies in all probability that ‘Christian’ was a nickname given by the populace of Antioch.”²⁰

¹⁷ Miriam Adeney, “Antioch: God’s Mission Amid Multicultural Networks,” in *God’s Mission in the Cities of the Bible*, ed. J. Tiersma-Watson, C.T. Accornero, and S. Burris (Skyforest, CA: Urban Loft Publishers, 2010), 12.

¹⁸ Jehu J. Hanciles, *Migration and the Making of Global Christianity* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2021), 132.

¹⁹ Simon J. Kistemaker, *Exposition of the Acts of the Apostles*, Hendriksen-Kistemaker New Testament Commentary. 1.7 (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 1990), 423.

²⁰ I. Howard Marshall, *Acts: An Introduction and Commentary*, Tyndale New Testament Commentary 5, Accordance electronic edition, version 2.9 (Downers Grove: InterVarsity Press, 1980), 215. John Stott: “Now it seems to have been the unbelieving public of Antioch, famed for their wit and nicknaming skill, who supposing that ‘Christ’ was a proper name rather than a title (the Christ or Messiah), coined the epithet *Christianoi*. It was probably more familiar and jocular than derisory.” John R.W. Stott, *The Message of Acts*, The Bible Speaks Today, Accordance electronic edition, version 1.6 (Downers Grove.: InterVarsity Press, 1994), 205.

The observable harmony between Jews and Gentiles was the reason that outsiders needed a new descriptive term. Previously, Jews maintained an extreme level of separation from Gentiles due to purity laws, dietary restrictions, and other cultural distinctives. Gentiles in Antioch had much greater diversity in their pagan rituals and cultural values but often segmented into various cultural groups. As the Way of Jesus permeated the city of Antioch, a new group of disciples was blending to create something else altogether. Richard Longenecker writes, “They saw that the ministry to Gentiles and the fellowship of Jews with Gentiles went beyond the bounds of what was usually permitted within Judaism. They also voiced an insight that the Christians themselves only saw clearly later on: Christianity is no mere variant of Judaism.”²¹ The internal faithfulness of the multicultural church in Antioch was externally fruitful as a witness to the larger society. Refugees fleeing persecution brought the gospel to the synagogues of the Jewish Diaspora and to the pagan citizens of Antioch. The citizens of Antioch couldn’t help but notice the compelling witness of the transformation that resulted.

The Church in Corinth – the body is one and has many members.

The churches established in Jerusalem and Antioch provide a description of disciples in fellowship across cultural differences. But is the description also prescription for churches located in diverse areas? When Paul wrote his letter to the church in Corinth, his prescription was for reconciliation not separation. The city context was an influential, cosmopolitan, pluralistic society filled with various cultures (i.e. “Jews and Greeks”) and social statuses (i.e. “slave and free”). Jayakumar Christian describes the cultural diversity as “a cosmopolitan mosaic of many cultures” with Greek, Latin, and Jewish cultures co-existing and “inhabited by Phoenicians and

²¹ Richard N. Longenecker, *Acts*, Expositors Bible Commentary 9, ed. Frank E. Gaebelein and J. D. Douglas, Accordance electronic edition, version 2.9 (Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 1984), 11:25-26.

Phrygians from the east.”²² Ekaputra Tupamahu describes the multicultural context of Corinth as also being multilingual: “The dominant languages were clearly Latin and Greek. But many more languages than those were spoken.”²³ The historic understanding of the gift of tongues in 1 Corinthians 14, that these were known native languages rather than miraculous ecstatic utterances, suggests that the Corinthian church mirrored multicultural and multilingual context.²⁴

The diversity in the Corinthian church may have initially led to divisiveness. Unlike the positive descriptions above of the Christians in Jerusalem and Antioch, Paul wrote his letter to repair the divisions lest they escalate to separation (1 Cor 1:10, 11:18). Leon Morris saw an external concern and an internal concern that demanded Paul’s attention: “Paul was troubled by the ‘tendency on the part of some members to make the break with pagan society as indefinite as possible ... The Church was in the world, as it had to be, but the world was in the Church, as it ought not to be,’” and “Paul was troubled about the divisions within the church.”²⁵ After addressing many divisive issues throughout his letter, Paul uses the metaphor of the body to

²² Jayakumar Christian, “Corinth: God’s Mission of Rediscovered Wisdom,” in *God’s Mission in the Cities of the Bible*, ed. J. Tiersma-Watson, C.T. Accornero, and S. Burris (Skyforest, CA: Urban Loft Publishers, 2010), 97.

²³ Ekaputra Tupamahu, *Contesting Languages: Heteroglossia and the Politics of Language in the Early Church* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2023), 57.

²⁴ W. H. Chong “How to Speak in Tongues: A Historical-Contextual Reading of Paul’s Use of Γλῶσσα/方言 in 1 Corinthians 12-14 from a Multilingual Diasporic Chinese Christian Church Context,” *Religions* 15, no. 3 (December 31, 2024): 1–13, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel15030288>. See also John Calvin who was noticing some variant interpretations for “tongues” in the 16th century. His footnote on 1 Corinthians 14:2 reads as follows: “It is remarked by Granville Penn, that ‘the context shows that the Apostle means, a language foreign to that of the auditors, and, therefore, not known to them’ — as ‘we learn from verse 21 that we are to supply ἕτερον — ‘other,’ not αγνωστη — ‘unknown.’ We have,’ he adds, ‘had lamentable proof of the abuse to which the latter injudicious rendering can be perverted in the hands of ignorant or insidious enthusiasm, by assuming the term to mean, ‘a tongue unknown to all mankind;’ and from thence, by an impious inference, supernatural and divine; instead of relatively, ‘unknown to another people.’ And yet, after all, ‘unknown’ is not the Apostle’s word, but only an Italic supplement suggested by the English revisers of the seventeenth century.” John Calvin, *Calvin’s Commentaries (Complete)*, trans. John King, Accordance electronic edition, version 3.2 (Edinburgh: Calvin Translation Society, 1847), Footnote 702.

²⁵ Leon Morris, *1 Corinthians: An Introduction and Commentary*, Tyndale New Testament Commentary 7, Accordance electronic edition, version 2.9 (Downers Grove: InterVarsity Press, 1985), 30.

illustrate his desire that the church be unified. Paul writes, “For just as the body is one and has many parts, and all the parts of that body, though many, are one body—so also is Christ” (1 Cor 12:12). Clearly, the local church ought to reflect the unity and diversity of the universal church. As Harold Mare observes, “By the words “So it is with Christ,” he means so it is with Christ’s body, the church.”²⁶ This universal aspect of Christ’s body is being compared to the local body of believers in Corinth. The phrase, “For just as the body is one and has many parts...” is here referring to the local body. Thus, the encouragement is for the unity and diversity of the local body to be like that of Christ’s body, the universal church. Paul will explain that the “many parts” are describing a variety of leaders and gifts. But first, Paul states that the “many parts” refer to the variety of ethnicities and cultures in the Corinthian church: “For we were all baptized by one Spirit into one body—whether Jews or Greeks, whether slaves or free—and we were all given one Spirit to drink” (1 Cor 12:13). Paul’s first letter to the church in Corinth was written to repair the unwelcome divisions that were caused by a broadly diverse group of disciples in a multicultural and multilingual setting. With all the divisions that needed to be addressed in his first letter, it is only by God’s grace that they were still one body when Paul had the opportunity to write a second letter to the church in Corinth.²⁷

²⁶ W. Harold Mare, *1 Corinthians*, Expositors Bible Commentary 10, ed. Frank E. Gaebelin and J. D. Douglas, Accordance electronic edition, version 2.9 (Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 1977), 11:12,13. Archibald Robertson agrees: “From one point of view Christ is the Head, but that is not the thought here. Here He is the whole Body, as being that which unites the members and makes them an organic whole. We might have had οὗτος καὶ ἡ ἐκκλησία, for Christ or the Church is only one Body with many members. The superfluous τοῦ σώματος after τὰ μέλη emphasizes the idea of unity; and some texts make this still more emphatic by interpolating τοῦ ἐνός after τοῦ σώματος. The human body is a unique illustration of unity in diversity.” Archibald Robertson, *The First Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*, A Critical and Exegetical Commentary, ed. Samuel Rolles Driver, Alfred Plummer, and Charles A. Briggs, Accordance electronic edition, version 1.4. (Edinburgh: T. & T. Clark, 1911), 12:12.

²⁷ Note the singular “church” in 2 Corinthians 1:1: “Paul, an apostle of Christ Jesus by God’s will, and Timothy our brother: To the church of God at Corinth, with all the saints who are throughout Achaia.”

The Church in Ephesus – he tore down the dividing wall of hostility.

Individualism is one of the more obvious characteristics of Western culture (in contrast to the collectivism of many other cultures).²⁸ Some biblical insights are lost when English-speaking Christians from the American majority culture are not in regular fellowship with Christians from the Majority World.²⁹ An insight that is often missed comes from the application of Ephesians 2:10, which says, “For we are his workmanship, created in Christ Jesus for good works, which God prepared ahead of time for us to do.” Christians in the American majority culture frequently apply this verse to the individual. But when Paul directs his comments to “you,” or more precisely “you all,” he is speaking to Gentiles collectively (Eph 2:11ff). He singles them out so that he can mention “we” and “us,” that is, Jews and Gentiles in one body.³⁰ The “workmanship” that Paul describes is the body made up of Jews and Gentiles; a body created for good works. Of course, individual salvation is in view (“you were dead,” “you are saved by grace”) but “we” are his *poiēma*, that is, his “workmanship” or “creation”.

Paul goes on to say that the church wasn’t simply made but was sacrificially bought:

But now in Christ Jesus, you who were far away have been brought near by the blood of Christ. For he is our peace, who made both groups one and tore down the dividing wall of hostility. In his flesh, he made of no effect the law consisting of commands and expressed

²⁸ See Duane Elmer, *Cross-Cultural Connections: Stepping Out and Fitting In Around the World* (Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity, 2002), 135-141. See also Jayson Georges who describes three types of cultures: “(1) *guilt-innocence cultures* are individualistic societies (mostly Western), where people who break the laws are guilty and seek justice or forgiveness to rectify a wrong, (2) *shame-honor cultures* describes collectivistic cultures (common in the East), where people shamed for not fulfilling group expectations seek to restore their honor before the community, and (3) *fear-power cultures* refers to animistic contexts (typically tribal or African), where people afraid of evil and harm pursue power over the spirit world through magical rituals.” Jayson Georges, *The 3D Gospel: Ministry in Guilt, Shame, and Fear Cultures* (Time Press, 2017), 10-11, Kindle.

²⁹ Hunn Choi believes “Churches need to be corrected through intercultural relationship with others. Without the witness of Christians of other cultures to correct our culturally conditioned understanding of Scripture, we will be forever captive in our own ethnic, racial, and cultural enclave.” Hunn Choi, “A New Form of a Multicultural Church for Today’s Multilingual Context.” (PhD diss., Asbury Theological Seminary, Wilmore, KY, 2023), 145.

³⁰ For example, note the shift from “we” to “you” in Ephesians 1:13 and the shift from “you” to “we” in Ephesians 2:3.

in regulations, so that he might create in himself one new man from the two, resulting in peace.” (Ephesians 3:13-15)

Jesus shed his blood to tear down the “dividing wall of hostility” to gather Jews and Gentiles into one new humanity. The dividing wall refers not only to the physical wall between the Court of the Gentiles and the inner temple complex in Jerusalem which was destroyed in A.D. 70, but more significantly to the religio-cultural barrier that separated Jews from Gentiles. Max Anders writes, “The barrier in question was the Mosaic law with its detailed holiness code, which made it all but impossible for faithful Jews to live in close proximity with Gentiles.” To separate what Christ has joined together in creation (2:10) and by his blood (2:13) would be a tragic divorce. Ken Baker, Chandler Im, and T.V. Thomas write, “The wonder of God’s kingdom is not just that there are believers from every culture; the true wonder is that when those from every culture come together as the church, mutual love replaces the walls of division.”³¹

Did Jesus only have the universal church in view when he shed his blood? Are local churches exempt from fellowshipping with other tribes and languages until the eschaton? Truly, the ingathering “from every tribe and language and people and nation” will be the Grand Finale (Rv 5:9). But until then, the breaking down of real-world hostilities happens in local churches. American Christians frequently show solidarity with persecuted Christians around the world by praying for them. But when persecuted Christians arrive in the United States to seek asylum they are often met with hostility and suspicion. Paul writes in Ephesians 4:4-6, “There is one body and one Spirit—just as you were called to one hope at your calling—one Lord, one faith, one baptism, one God and Father of all, who is above all and through all and in all.” Charles Van Engen says, “We do not confess ‘holy catholic churches,’ or ‘families of God,’ or ‘peoples of

³¹ Ken Baker, Chandler H. Im, T.V. Thomas, “The Mission of the Church through Understanding and Pursuing Intercultural Unity,” in *Scattered and Gathered: A Global Compendium of Diaspora Missiology*, Rev. Ed. (Carlisle, UK: Langham Publishing, 2020), 412.

God,' or 'bodies of Christ,' or 'new Israels.' In the biblical view of the church the plural refers only to geographical location, not existential being."³² The unity and diversity represented in the universal body of Christ is to be celebrated and, as far as possible, embodied in local churches. Jesus shed his blood to gather his church from East and West, North and South. It would be a tragedy to divide his body over the color of the doorknobs, or worse, the color of a person's skin.

Additional examples could be given from the New Testament to reinforce how the witness of the church was made stronger through the harmonious diversity displayed by the disciples.³³ Jews and Gentiles struggled to "resocialize"³⁴ into a new humanity for the glory of God. Jews abandoned obsolete food restrictions, purity rituals, and worshipping on Saturday and began eating meals and worshipping together with Gentiles. Gentiles, on the other hand, gave up pagan rituals and switched their allegiance from Caesar to confessing Jesus as Lord. Moving toward greater unity in diversity today won't typically require the same level of sacrifice as it did for first century Christians, and yet the pursuit is too often forsaken for a more comfortable Christianity.

³² Charles Van Engen, *Mission on the Way: Issues in Mission Theology* (Grand Rapids: Baker Books, 1996), 106.

³³ After providing similar case studies for the church in Jerusalem, Antioch, and Philippi, Thorsten Prill sums up the multicultural nature of the churches planted by Paul. Prill writes, "According to Luke, a similar ethnic, cultural and social mix could be found in the churches that were set up by Paul and Silas in Thessalonica, Berea, and Corinth. In Acts 17:4 he informs us that the first Christian congregation in Thessalonica was composed of Jews, a great number of God-fearing Gentiles and a considerable number of leading Macedonian women. In 17:12 he mentions that the new Christian church in Berea included a larger group of Jews and some Greek women and men." Thorsten Prill, "Migration, Mission and the Multi-Ethnic Church," *Evangelical Review of Theology* 33:4 (2009), 338.

³⁴ Samuel Escobar writes, "The faith of Jesus Christ had to be lived and interpreted in dialogue with narrow Jewish provincialism, with skeptical and sophisticated Greek philosophizing, with the Roman cult of the supreme principles of law, order and power, and with the deeply attractive spiritual experiences of the mystery religions. It was not only an intellectual task but also a resocializing experience and a spiritual struggle." Samuel Escobar, *The New Global Mission: The Gospel from Everywhere to Everyone*, (Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity, 2003), 40.

3. Contemporary Approaches

Racial, cultural, and linguistic diversity are not the only types of diversity found in a local church. Still, the biblical evidence is clear: Where there are disagreements or differences between brothers and sisters in Christ, they should be reconciled within the local church. Reconciliation and healing of divisions should happen in every congregation in every zip code throughout America regardless of how diverse the zip code. The four approaches described below represent lesser to greater levels of diversity within churches located in a multicultural context. Principles of unity gleaned from this study can be applied to all sorts of divisions within the body.

Segregation: The Monocultural Church in a Multicultural Neighborhood

There are many reasons (some valid) a monocultural church might remain monocultural in a multicultural neighborhood. In some historically white neighborhoods, a majority culture church may have been too slow to recognize the increase in diversity of their surroundings. Members may be complacent. Leaders may be ill-equipped to lead change. Such a church may have a willingness to welcome their diverse neighbors but never considered if there was warrant biblically or how to pursue it practically. Ethnic minority churches may have planted initially because of a language barrier or with the express purpose of reaching a specific unreached people group. But now the neighborhood has changed around them, and they don't know how to get unstuck from their basic identity as a monocultural church. Paul said, "I have become all things to all people, so that I may by every possible means save some." (1 Cor 9:22). Paul's flexibility and fortitude as an apostle doesn't always come naturally to local church leaders and members. Eric Costanzo, Daniel Yang, and Matthew Soerens offer a slight concession: "One church cannot be all things to all people, but in seeing itself beyond its immediate locality, it has a better chance at becoming more things to more people. And as this happens, church leaders will

usually seek to grow their membership toward higher levels of racial diversity and multiethnicity.”³⁵ To become more things to more people, local churches could ask diagnostic questions such as: “Do our neighbors know they are welcome here?” and “What have we done to prepare for them?”

Justification for a monocultural church to stubbornly resist extending themselves to their multicultural neighbors cannot be found in Scripture. Fumitaka Matsuoka writes, “Whenever the church consciously or unconsciously caters exclusively to one race or class, it loses the spiritual force of the welcoming each other posture and risks becoming little more than a social club with a thin veneer or religiosity.”³⁶ Even those churches that have a clear conscience that their situation justifies their homogeneity (due to a specific target group or a temporary situation) should realize that they will be at a disadvantage in their multicultural neighborhood and may inadvertently be a negative witness to society. If a church has historically been monocultural but desires to become more multicultural they will find it difficult to win over their neighbors who have already branded them as “the white church” or “the Hispanic church”. In a 1960 interview on NBC’s “Meet the Press” King said,

Any church that stands against integration, and that has a segregated body, is standing against the spirit and the teachings of Jesus Christ and it fails to be a true witness. But this is something that the church would have to do itself. I don’t think church integration will come through legal processes. I might say that my church is not a segregating church. It is segregated but not segregating. It would welcome white members.”³⁷

³⁵ Eric Costanzo, Daniel Yang, Matthew Soerens, *Inalienable: How Marginalized Kingdom Voices Can Help Save the American Church* (Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 2022), 55.

³⁶ Fumitaka Matsuoka, *The Color of Faith: Building Community in a Multiracial Society* (Cleveland, United Church Press, 1998), 125.

³⁷ Martin Luther King Jr., “The Most Segregated Hour in America” Meet the Press. Recorded April 17, 1960. Video of interview. https://youtu.be/1q881g1L_d8?si=qrjSNJCusanNI9DY.

King’s contrast between his predominately Black church that was “segregated” (out of necessity) from the “segregating” white church (out of prejudice) is an important point. Most monocultural churches are not opposed to greater diversity, but members of the community are still not going to show up if they perceive the church as segregated by race or ethnicity. Regardless of the cause, John Perkins believes the segregated church is an open wound:

Our poor black communities cannot hide the effect that racism and oppression have had on us...The wound of the black church is an open wound, bleeding in public for everyone to see...But as an evangelist to the white church, I’ve also learned to see the hidden wounds of white Christians. No one ever put a chain on another human being without tying the other end to themselves.³⁸

There may be societal or cultural reasons why a church in a multicultural neighborhood remains monocultural. The vast majority are not racist or nativist. But given that there is no example in the New Testament of a segregated church, even a healthy monocultural church in a multicultural neighborhood should be viewed as the exception and not the rule. Ken Baker, Chandler H. Im, and T.V. Thomas write,

All of God’s people and every gathering of his church must cross the boundaries of culture and make intentional efforts to move towards one another as we all move towards Christ. This is a lifestyle absolutely foreign to the unbeliever and largely unnatural even to the redeemed... Intercultural unity is the supernatural and interdependent relationship between believers of different cultures which is made possible only through the reconciling work of Christ on the cross.³⁹

Cooperation: The Multitenant Church in a Multicultural Neighborhood

Thankfully, there are many churches in diverse contexts who pursue greater levels of cooperation with other churches. One of the ways churches cooperate is by sharing space. Of course, cooperation between churches is not limited to the use of space but a multitenant church

³⁸ Charles Marsh and John M. Perkins, *Welcoming Justice: God’s Movement Toward Beloved Community* (Downers Grove, Ill: IVP Books, 2020), Location 506-525, Kindle.

³⁹ Baker, Im, and Thomas, 412.

approach is a common form of cooperation in many diverse and densely populated neighborhoods. A multitenant church is defined here as a church that owns their building and is willing to share the space with other churches, often with a rental agreement. The multitenant church in a multicultural neighborhood can be a positive step towards cooperation both for the owner who may need financial help to maintain the facility and for the tenant church who needs space at a discounted rate. Mark Clifton writes, “When a declining church opens its building to a new church plant (or maybe even multiple new church plants), it can play a critical role in helping the church plant make it through a key transition point.”⁴⁰ Opening the doors of the church can be an act of generous hospitality.

Churches cooperating from the same shared location is a positive step towards greater unity. But as Baker, Im, and Thomas point out, “The mere co-existence of ethnic congregations throughout a city does not adequately demonstrate the displayed unity of the body of Christ envisioned in the gospel. Celebrating Jesus together across cultures and fellowshiping with one another in personal relationship powerfully demonstrates unity in diversity.”⁴¹ Similarly, housing two or more churches in one building with a cooperative agreement doesn’t fully display the unity of the body of Christ. The relationship may remain fruitful, but it might also quickly devolve into a frustrating experience for both parties. Lack of communication or poor handling of various schedules and expectations can quickly sour the relationship. The landlord church will always have the final say in what times and what spaces are available to the various tenant churches. Rather than genuine fellowship, the landlord-tenant relationship can soon become an anxiety-ridden nightmare. When viewed as a temporary arrangement with clear expectations, the

⁴⁰ Mark Clifton, *Reclaiming Glory: Revitalizing Dying Churches* (Nashville: B & H, 2016), 42.

⁴¹ Baker, Im, and Thomas, 414.

relationship can remain extremely positive and may even result in a positive witness to the community. Yet, from an outside perspective, two or more churches meeting separately in the same location draws public attention to the fact that they are, in fact, not meeting together.

Assimilation: The Multiethnic Church in a Multicultural Neighborhood

Multiethnic is the generally accepted term for churches that are embracing greater heterogeneity within one local church. Gary McIntosh and Alan McMahan prefer to use the term multiethnic because “this word fits both the biblical concept and current understanding of the best [terminology].”⁴² Many multiethnic churches throughout the U.S. desire for their membership to accurately represent the diversity of their community. Statistical equivalence is not the goal but may be a useful benchmark towards progress. Any effort towards joining together all the disciples in one geographical location should be commended. Assimilating foreign born refugees into a community with upwardly mobile suburban moms and homeless drug addicts can be a beautiful picture of unity in diversity. Some ethnic minorities are content to be assimilated into white majority spaces. First generation immigrants may be willing to attend in a language they don’t understand for the sake of their children and grandchildren. Multiethnic churches will often provide translation services to facilitate faster assimilation into the body. This can also be a positive step for the ethnic minority church that was previously renting space from the majority culture church. Moving from cooperation in a multitenant church relationship to assimilation can mean moving out of the basement on Sundays at 3PM, for example, to the main worship area at 11:00AM. In some ways, this would mark the fulfillment of Martin Luther

⁴² Gary L. McIntosh and Alan McMahan, *Being the Church in a Multi-Ethnic Community: Why It Matters and How It Works* (Indianapolis: Wesleyan, 2012), 26.

King Jr.'s desire for greater integration in the American church. More multiethnic churches could turn the most segregated hour to an increasingly more integrated hour in America.

Though there are many commendable virtues in a multiethnic church, there may be cultural blind spots as well. A church can simultaneously be both multiethnic and monocultural. This isn't true of all multiethnic churches, but as Dougherty, Chavez, and Emerson point out, "For whites, diversity is pursued by trying to attract people of color who will not challenge white congregants' views and practices."⁴³ Derwin Gray recognized some multiethnic churches led by white majority culture pastors were overlooking some of the issues that were important to ethnic minorities in their congregation. Gray writes, "Sadly, many multiethnic megachurches are silent on issues of racial justice and systemic injustice. Recently, many minorities have left these kinds of churches because it was a "thin" diversity that lacked commitment to a holistic, gospel-shaped diversity, in which accommodation is realized, not simply assimilation."⁴⁴ Gray then quotes from a 2018 article from the *Detroit Times* entitled "Why are People of Color Leaving White Evangelical Churches?":

The exodus started the day after the George Zimmerman verdict. We were mourning. And we went to church on Sunday morning hoping we would hear a word of comfort. And many of us who went to either multi-racial or predominately white spaces found no word of comfort. We found no word at all.⁴⁵

The public witness of the American church was being written about negatively in a major publication. The "thin diversity" that had been cultivated proved to be too thin for some racial minorities. Karen González shares a similar testimony:

I was told that the church valued diversity—later I discovered that this actually meant

⁴³ Dougherty, Chavez, and Emerson, 660.

⁴⁴ Derwin Gray, *Building a Multiethnic Church: A Gospel Vision of Love, Grace, and Reconciliation in a Divided World* (Nashville: Thomas Nelson, 2021), 20.

⁴⁵ Gray, 20.

that they valued seeing Black and brown faces in the congregation but that they did not welcome Black and brown people as teachers, leaders, and decision-makers. In essence, the church also wanted my assimilation into their way of being. It was acceptable to be brown as long as I talked and behaved like the majority-white congregation and knew my place.⁴⁶

To his credit, Gray recognizes the blind spots of the multiethnic church and then goes on to address many of them in his book. The “come to us” approach of the multiethnic/monocultural church is still lacking a few key ingredients that were omnipresent in the biblical evidence presented above: linguistic hospitality and mutuality.

Harmonization: The Multicultural Church in a Multicultural Neighborhood

A multicultural church is a church that recognizes the unique strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities that each member brings from their cultural background. Rather than obscure differences (either intentionally or unintentionally) through assimilation into the dominant culture, a multicultural church embraces the strengths that each culture contributes. As has been true of all the previous approaches, there is no perfect church. Hunn Choi writes, “Any proposed multicultural church will reflect the heavenly church imperfectly. However, it begins with the end in view. It attempts to overcome, exceed, and transcend the limits imposed by race, culture, class, and language.”⁴⁷ Jews and Gentiles had to make accommodations to live harmoniously with one another. Jews laid aside dietary restrictions. Gentiles switched allegiances from Caesar

⁴⁶ Karen González, *Beyond Welcome: Centering Immigrants in Our Christian Response to Immigration* (Grand Rapids, Michigan: Brazos Press, a division of Baker Publishing Group, 2022), 18-19. In addition to assimilation in the local church, González offers her perspective on assimilating into the larger American society: “The message of assimilation makes me uncomfortable because it requires me to celebrate the loss of other people’s culture, traditions, and languages in order to alleviate the fears that white people, including Christians, might have about a diverse society where their position as power brokers of society may be threatened...I refuse to communicate that message because it is not my job to appease privileged white Christians at the expense of the dignity of immigrants. Nor is it my job to absolve anyone of their Christian responsibility to welcome and love immigrants...” González, 17.

⁴⁷ Choi, 93-94.

to Jesus. These are not small changes and there will be many missteps along the way. But moving toward one another in love is not only described but also prescribed in Scripture.

One of the greatest challenges to becoming a multicultural church is how best to provide linguistic hospitality to foreign-born neighbors. Not every multicultural church will also be multilingual, but growing diversity in US neighborhoods necessitates a growing number of churches who will confront the issue. Praying, singing, and preaching in a person's heart language is not simply a preference like musical styles or the color of the doorknobs. Language is a major part of a person's cultural identity and is their greatest means of self-expression. In an article for Christianity Today, Emily Belz quotes Bible translator Harriet Hill: "When God speaks to us in the language we learned in our mother's arms, the message of his acceptance of our identity penetrates the very fiber of our being."⁴⁸ Technology now allows for simultaneous translation into almost any known language. Yet, as helpful as translation services are, they will never remove the need to worship God from a person's first language. A multicultural church will find ways to use technology in joint services but also to provide space for additional gatherings or small groups for various languages to be spoken. Hunn Choi writes,

Language is powerful. When the majority group honors the languages of the minority groups, power in the church can shift. Though the official language is English, if a minority, ethnic, or heritage language is not marginalized or ignored but honored and respected equally as honorable and respectful as the others or the dominant language, this leads to mutual respect, honor, cohesion, cooperation, and appreciation.⁴⁹

Meanwhile, the children and grandchildren, who are rapidly assimilating into the host culture, will usually be better served hearing and speaking the language of the new host culture. Because

⁴⁸ Emily Belz, "How NYC Churches Guard Endangered Languages," Christianity Today <https://www.christianitytoday.com/2025/01/how-nyc-churches-guard-endangered-languages/>.

⁴⁹ Choi, 24.

the needs of first and second generations will be different, a multicultural church provides the best opportunity for multigenerational worship.

Linguistic hospitality will often encourage another often missing in multiethnic churches: mutuality. Elizabeth Conde-Frazier writes, “The first step in multicultural living is hospitality. It is a practice which brings us into closer alignment with the basic values of the kingdom...Hospitality encourages mutuality.”⁵⁰ Mutuality is preferred to unbiblical partiality and unrealistic equality. James writes, “My brothers and sisters, do not show favoritism as you hold on to the faith in our glorious Lord Jesus Christ.” (Jas 2:1) On the other extreme, equality presents an idealistic goal that is impossible to achieve. One advocate for equality in multicultural churches believes “A church cannot be truly multicultural without a strong sense of equality. There can be instances of ethnic/racial justice where true multiculturalism does not exist, but there can be no real multiculturalism without ethnic/racial justice, i.e., without ethnic/racial equality, in all aspects of church life.” The New Testament authors recognized that local churches would be made up of rich and poor, Jew and Gentile, male and female. Power imbalances will exist. The goal is not for perfect equality but rather biblical mutuality. The apostle Paul takes aim at the power struggles in the Corinthian church when he writes,

On the contrary, those parts of the body that are weaker are indispensable. And those parts of the body that we consider less honorable, we clothe these with greater honor, and our unrespectable parts are treated with greater respect, which our respectable parts do not need. Instead, God has put the body together, giving greater honor to the less honorable, so that there would be no division in the body, but that the members would have the same concern for each other. So if one member suffers, all the members suffer with it; if one member is honored, all the members rejoice with it. Now you are the body of Christ, and individual members of it. (1 Cor 11:22-27)

⁵⁰ Elizabeth Conde-Frazier, S. Steve Kang, and Gary A. Parrett, *A Many Colored Kingdom: Multicultural Dynamics for Spiritual Formation* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2004), 171.

Paul’s solution was to practice mutuality within the body. Each person in the church should submit to one another (Eph 5:21) and humbly consider others as more important than themselves (Phi 2:3-4). Each member regardless of cultural background should consider, “that God has put the body together” and that showing honor to one another eliminates “division in the body.”

Multicultural churches provide the best context for unity to be displayed through diversity. An imperfect and ever-shifting balance between full integration into one body while maintaining cultural distinctives (especially language) can be challenging. Charles Van Engen warns, “too strong an emphasis on universality will drive us toward uniformity and blind us to cultural distinctives. Too strong an emphasis on particularity will push us toward exclusivist homogeneity or fragmented ethnocentrism and create serious questions about our oneness in Jesus Christ.”⁵¹ The need for oneness in Jesus Christ is essential for the inner life of the multicultural church but it is also essential for external witness as Justo Gonzalez points out:

If the Christian gospel is not powerful enough within the church itself to lead us through the difficulties of ethnic conflict and cultural dissonance, we can hardly claim that it is good news to a world going through similar difficulties on a much larger scale. The church must be one, not primarily for its own sake—or its own order, its own sense of security, etc. The church must be one because a fragmented church is not much help to a fragmented world.”⁵²

⁵¹ Charles Van Engen, “Is the Church for Everyone? Planting Multi-ethnic Congregations in North America,” <http://ojs.globalmissiology.org/index.php/english/article/view/122/353>, 4. Accessed April 28, 2025.

⁵² Justo L. Gonzalez, *For the Healing of the Nations*, (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 1999), 23, Kindle.

4. The Role for Diaspora Christians

Last year, a net increase of 2.8 million international migrants accounted for 84% of the nation's highest population increase in decades.⁵³ Births outnumbering deaths by nearly 519,000 contributed the other 16%. A similar trend is occurring in the American church, but instead of driving growth, international migrants are drastically slowing the decline. Deaths of churches outnumber births by nearly 1,500 in America.⁵⁴ From 2000 to 2020, the median attendance size of American churches decreased significantly from 137 to 65 attendees in weekly worship services.⁵⁵ In short, fewer American churches are filled with fewer American Christians. Yet, the steep decline would be far worse if not for international migration. Most Americans would be surprised to learn that “86 percent of the immigrant population in North America are likely to either be Christians or become Christians.”⁵⁶ Truly, “global Christianity has already been helping to save some streams of American Christianity from an all-out free fall and decline.”⁵⁷ Through lived experience and vibrant faith, diaspora Christians are offering hope and help to a church in crisis.

Sam George and Miriam Adeney remind us that “diaspora” is “a Greek biblical word, meaning ‘scattered’ or ‘dispersion.’ This term was originally used in the context of the Jewish dispersion and life in exile, but it has been increasingly used to refer to all forms of displaced

⁵³ “Net International Migration Drives Highest U.S. Population Growth in Decades” US Census Bureau, December 19, 2024, <https://www.census.gov/newsroom/press-releases/2024/population-estimates-international-migration.html>.

⁵⁴ Aaron Earls, “Protestant Church Closures Outpace Openings in U.S.” Lifeway Research, May 25, 2021, <https://research.lifeway.com/2021/05/25/protestant-church-closures-outpace-openings-in-u-s/>.

⁵⁵ Thumma.

⁵⁶ Tennent, 1:38.

⁵⁷ Costanzo, Yang and Soerens, 45.

people, including refugees.”⁵⁸ Diaspora Christians, then, are Christian brothers and sisters who are foreign born and have migrated to the United States for various reasons. The experience of leaving a homeland to scrape out a new life in a foreign land enables diaspora Christians to identify more with the Jewish exiles and the persecuted church than with the American or Western church. Migration is a formative experience for God’s people. Jehu Hanciles believes, “the biblical tradition and message would be meaningless without migration or migrant activity.”⁵⁹ Israel became a nation during four hundred years of slavery followed by forty years of wilderness wanderings. The early church spread out from Jerusalem due to persecution.

Hanciles writes,

Like many other new religious movements in the Roman Empire, Christianity began as a religion of migrant-outsiders (*paroikoi*) or people on the margins; and its astounding growth underscores the capacity of migrants and migrant movements to generate historical change. The embeddedness of many immigrants in far-flung diaspora (or social) networks was a major factor in the rapid spread of Christianity. The Jewish population, for instance, formed a network of diaspora communities settled in most of the empire’s provinces—about a million Jews resided in Egypt alone.”⁶⁰

The Jewish Diaspora may have been more instrumental to the spread of Christianity than the Roman road and the Greek language. Apostles (like Paul and Barnabas) and evangelists (like Philip) and tens of thousands of anonymous disciples successfully brought the good news to far-flung corners of the Roman Empire. Being people on the margins was the common experience for these pre-Constantinian Christians. The greatest periods of Christian expansion have largely

⁵⁸ Sam George and Miriam Adeney, *Refugee Diaspora: Missions Amid the Greatest Humanitarian Crisis of the World* (Pasadena: William Carey, 2018), xxv.

⁵⁹ Hanciles, 88.

⁶⁰ Hanciles, 162.

come by the hands and feet of marginalized Christians on the move.⁶¹ The New Testament was written to encourage Christians experiencing displacement, persecution, and trials. Most letters were addressed to “the saints” in a particular city or region (e.g. Ro 1:7, Ep 1:1) but other letters were written to “elect exiles, dispersed abroad” (1 Pet 1:1) or “the twelve tribes dispersed abroad” (Jas 1:1). A major encouragement for these Christians living on the margins was, “Consider it a great joy, my brothers and sisters, whenever you experience various trials, because you know that the testing of your faith produces endurance. And let endurance have its full effect, so that you may be mature and complete, lacking nothing.” (Jas 1:2-4). The faith, endurance, maturity, and joy that results from overcoming difficult trials like persecution, exile, migration, and marginalization strengthens diaspora Christians who, in turn, strengthen the churches of which they are a part.

Today, diaspora Christians exhibit a resiliency and determination that is needed if American churches are going to influence American society. Mark DeYmaz describes how diaspora Christians are effective at reaching other diaspora groups when he writes, “These diaspora communities are built on mutual understanding, shared struggle and a commitment to reach, serve and bless others who have navigated immigration or similar challenges of cultural adaptation.”⁶² Thanks to their “gift of tongues” and shared experience with fellow migrant-outsiders, diaspora Christians are perhaps best situated to reach the 28 million residents from the

⁶¹ Broadly speaking, the greatest periods of Christian expansion are from the persecution in Jerusalem to shortly after the persecution of Diocletian in AD 303, and from the start of the Protestant Reformation in AD 1517 to today.

⁶² Mark DeYmaz, “How Immigrant Churches Advance the Mission of God: And a Call for Mutuality Through Healthy Multiethnic Churches,” National Association of Evangelicals, February 3, 2025, <https://www.nae.org/immigrant-churches-advance-mission-god-mark-deymaz/>.

228 unreached people groups living in diaspora in the United States.⁶³ But many diaspora Christians recognize the need to reach the broader American society with the gospel. Miriam Adeney writes about the specific impact of Spanish-speaking Christians in reaching all segments of society: “Among the poor, and also among the comfortable, witness to this new life is spreading through the neighborhoods of U.S. cities at the grassroots because of Latinos. Some believe that is why they were led to the US: to revitalize the faith of this nation.”⁶⁴ Or, as one Burmese Christian put it “God brought thousands and thousands of us Burmese Christians to America, we believe, to help revitalize American churches.”⁶⁵ American Christians in historically black and historically white monocultural churches must recognize that “we are incomplete without each other. The church should not claim to be “the body of Christ” without its essential character of intercultural unity. It is a great tragedy when congregations demonstrate through their networks that they think they are complete within their own linguistic, ethnic, or affinity group.”⁶⁶ Will the historically white and historically black American church persist in remaining segregated from this new group of fellow Christians? Will the American church seek to cooperate with or assimilate these diaspora communities? Or, better yet, will the American church begin to harmonize with their diaspora Christian brothers and sisters in multicultural churches throughout the US?

The monocultural, multitenant, multiethnic, and multicultural churches have already been described above. But which approach offers the best path forward for unity with diaspora

⁶³ “Global Status of Evangelical Christianity Reports,” International Mission Board, January 1, 2025, <https://grd.imb.org/research-data/>.

⁶⁴ Miriam Adeney, “Latino Diaspora Ministries in the USA,” in *Scattered and Gathered: A Global Compendium of Diaspora Missiology*. Revised Edition (Carlisle, UK: Langham Publishing, 2020), 498.

⁶⁵ Costanzo, Yang, and Soerens, 43.

⁶⁶ Baker, Im, and Thomas, 413.

Christians? The path of segregation cannot be the answer. The American church is being given another opportunity to “integrate,” this time with immigrants (though the issue of black/white segregation persists). Once again, segregated and marginalized Christians are not waiting around for a “moribund church” to act. Kwabena Asamoah-Gyadu believes “that it is now the turn of the churches of the South to revive the Western church. The role of diasporas in the midst of the secular West is therefore critically important. Indeed, many immigrant churches and their leaders have come to define themselves as ‘missionaries’ who are ‘planning to reach out not only to their own nationals, but to [Western] society as a whole’ in the bid to bring revival to ‘dead’ churches.”⁶⁷ Even cut off from the broader American church, diaspora Christians are proving effective at reaching their neighbors with the gospel. In homes and storefronts, diaspora Christians are finding spaces to gather in language specific churches and are leading a “quiet revival” across the American landscape.⁶⁸ Though American Christians should recognize they have more in common with diaspora Christians than with their American-born Catholic neighbor or Muslim coworker, this divine family connection is lost on most American Christians. Just 3 in 10 evangelical Christians say they have heard immigration discussed at their local church in a way that encouraged them to reach out to the immigrants in their community.⁶⁹ American

⁶⁷ J. Kwabena Asamoah-Gyadu, “Prayer and Power from the South African Diaspora Churches on Mission,” in *Scattered and Gathered: A Global Compendium of Diaspora Missiology*, Rev. Ed. (Carlisle, UK: Langham Publishing, 2020), 379-380.

⁶⁸ For example, Boston’s Quiet Revival from 1965 to today as documented by researchers at the Emmanuel Gospel Center. Jeff Bass, the executive director of EGC says, “the growth was happening in non-mainline systems, non-English speaking systems, denominations you have never heard of, churches that meet in storefronts, churches that meet on Sunday afternoons. See Brian Corcoran, “Understanding Boston’s Quiet Revival,” *Emmanuel Research Review*, no. 94, Boston, 2014, <https://www.egc.org/blog-2/2016/10/13/understanding-bostons-quiet-revival>.

⁶⁹ “2024 Evangelical Views on Immigration Study,” Lifeway Research, February 2024, <https://research.lifeway.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/2024-Evangelical-Views-on-Immigration-Report.pdf>.

Christians are either excluding or ignoring their fellow brothers and sisters in Christ and are neglecting to share the gospel with immigrants who are not Christians. J. D. Payne writes,

The call to reach the nations that have migrated to our neighborhoods is not a call to neglect to send missionaries to Majority World countries where large numbers of unreached peoples exist...However, something is missionally malignant whenever we are willing to make great sacrifices to travel the world to reach a people group but are not willing to walk across the street.⁷⁰

Something is also missionally malignant when American Christians remain segregated and cut off from their fellow brothers and sisters. For the sake of the gospel, there must be a better way.

Recognizing that segregation from other brothers and sisters is not an option, some churches have generously opened their doors to provide space for diaspora Christians to meet. The church fellowship hall or gym can be used to great effect by resilient immigrant churches. Even the sanctuary might be made available if the immigrant church is willing to meet at non-traditional times. The cooperation between separate churches can give the tenant immigrant group a temporary place to call home and can provide the landlord church the necessary funds to keep the facility maintained. Again, the multitenant church relationship may be a positive short-term relationship, but Thorsten Prill believes it negates the principle of unity all Christians are called to pursue. He writes, “Christians, whatever their ethno-cultural background, have a new identity. They are united through their common faith in Christ. This principle of unity in Christ calls Christians to integrate Christian migrants into existing indigenous churches. To establish completely separate, independent migrant churches would contradict the Christian doctrine of unity.”⁷¹ Further, this separation will mean that church members in the American church will largely remain cut off from the members of the immigrant churches aside from a few joint pot-

⁷⁰ J. D. Payne, *Pressure Points: Twelve Global Issues Shaping the Face of the Church* (Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2013), 69.

⁷¹ Prill, 343.

lucks. The lessons American Christians could learn from diaspora Christians will never be learned because one part of the body is still mostly cut off from the other.

Many American Christians will opt to welcome and assimilate migrant groups into their multiethnic group. Once again, this is a step in the right direction. However, if the multiethnic church remains monocultural and expects everyone else to assimilate into the identity of the dominant culture, the voice of diaspora Christians will continue to be marginalized. It isn't much comfort to realize that the marginalization of minorities and of diaspora Christians is not intentional, but it is out of ignorance. When church leaders are so captive to their own culture that they cannot see the value provided by other cultures (e.g. Western individualism being tempered by collectivism). It is rare for American church leaders, even in multiethnic churches, to discover their own cultural blind spots and be open to lessons learned from diaspora Christians. The multiethnic church is a step towards greater unity in diversity, but if diaspora Christians are being asked to check their cultural identity, linguistic ability, and life experiences at the door they aren't going to come in.

Though the multicultural church is the more biblically faithful and evangelistically effective approach, harmony within a multicultural church is not a given. Harvey Kwiyani surveyed several multicultural churches for his doctoral dissertation. He laments that even in some multicultural churches, the congregants "looked to heaven together but did not look at one another."⁷² However, he did run across a multicultural church that was "well integrated both in its demographics and its theology. It embodied the true definition of a multicultural congregation; the membership included a good mix of white Americans and Latinos and African peoples."⁷³

⁷² Harvey C. Kwiyani, "Diaspora, Hybridity, and Theology," in *A Hybrid World: Diaspora, Hybridity, and Missio Dei*, eds. Sadiri Joy Tira and Juliet Lee Uytanlet (Pasadena, CA: William Carey Publishing, 2020), 46.

⁷³ Kwiyani.

What made the difference? Everyone in the church was encouraged to adopt the identity of a foreigner. He observed that “Central to this congregation’s hybrid self-understanding was the lead [white American] pastor’s theological emphasis that every member of the congregation is a foreigner, including the Americans, and that only God was the host. As guests of God, each member of the congregation was required to keep the community as hospitable as possible for everyone.” When all members are on an even footing hospitality and mutuality can flourish. Harmonious diversity in the local church doesn’t come naturally. In fact, some attempts at building healthy multicultural churches will fail. James Plueddemann believes “Even though global cooperation will always be pestered by misunderstanding in this fallen world, a growing understanding, appreciation and harmony is possible and necessary”⁷⁴ Coming together in one multicultural church body should be the rule with multitenant and multiethnic churches being the exception. Though DeYmaz prefers the term “multiethnic,” he accurately summarizes the result of harmonious diversity in a healthy multicultural church:

I believe it’s long past time for us to move beyond the binary view of “immigrant” versus “non-immigrant” churches. While honoring the contributions of immigrant congregations, we should also seek together to build healthy multiethnic churches that empower immigrant voices, hold space for first, second and third generation seekers and believers, and more fully represent God’s love for all people in a single body, patterned, for example, after the New Testament churches at Antioch, Ephesus and Rome (see Acts 11:19–26, 13:1; Ephesians 2:10–4:6)⁷⁵

A variety of churches are needed to reach the increasing diversity of peoples across the American landscape. As demonstrated above, there is also a growing need for intentional diversity in local churches, especially those located in diverse neighborhoods. The harmonious diversity that is experienced in a multicultural church will not be the utopia that some advocates

⁷⁴ James E. Plueddemann, *Leading Across Cultures: Effective Ministry and Mission in the Global Church* (Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 2009), 212.

⁷⁵ DeYmaz.

propose. Wanting every local church to “look like heaven” is idealistic and unrealistic since not every tribe, language, people, and nation will be found in every neighborhood. Instead, every church should seek to become more things to more people and to “look like the neighborhood,” so long as diversity is biblically motivated and not merely for the optics. The challenge of starting and strengthening multicultural churches in multicultural neighborhoods may not bring the utopian “heaven on earth,” but by God’s grace it may result in “heterotopia”⁷⁶ where the unity that Jesus prayed for (Jn 17:21) is not threatened by the diversity he paid for (Ep 2:13ff; Rv 5:9). Diaspora Christians are uniquely prepared through experiences of displacement, migration, and marginalization to move the American church towards harmonious diversity. A revitalized and reunified American church that results from the gospel co-labors of historically white Christians, historically black Christians, and Christians living in diaspora in the United States will present a more beautiful and complete “final apologetic” to a secular society.

⁷⁶ “The concept of heterotopia is used to describe reconciliatory diversity, which is characteristic of an inclusive postmodern church which is a space where unity is not threatened by diversity, where the one is not afraid of the Other...The ecclesia becomes a heterotopia when both space and time are transcended by making hegemony obsolete, and creating space and time for the Other in the here-and-now of this immanent real world.” Tanya van Wyk, “Church as Heterotopia,” *Hervormde Teologiese Studies* 70, no. 1 (2014): 1-7, <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/church-as-heterotopia/docview/1680763867/se-2>.

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